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INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISHDA MUXANDISLIK YO'NALISHI TALABALARI UCHUN SAMARALI ESLAB QOLISH USULLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ingliz tili butun dunyo bo'ylab muloqot qilish uchun eng muhim tilga aylandi, ammo uni chet tili sifatida o'rganish ko'plab qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bir nechta yodlash usullaridan foydalanish o'quv jarayonini martaba, akademik yoki kundalik hayotda ustunlik qilishda farq qilishi mumkin. Til o'rganish hammasi ham oson emas, shuning uchun ham bir nechta samarali yodlash usullarini topish va amalga oshirish haqiqatan ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Ta'lim uchun muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishi uchun muhim bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni eslab qolish va eslab qolishning samarali usullaridan foydalanish juda muhimdir. Ushbu maqola ingliz tili texnik lug'atini o'rganish va muhandislik talabalarini uchun xotirani yaxshilashda turli xil yodlash usullarini o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilni o'rganish, xotira, yodlash usullari, yodlash usullari va mnemotexnika.

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ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЗАПОМИНАНИЯ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ ИНЖЕНЕРНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Английский язык стал самым важным языком общения во всем мире, но изучение его как иностранного языка сопряжено с множеством проблем. Использование нескольких техник запоминания может разнообразить процесс обучения, когда речь идет о достижениях в карьере, учебе или повседневной жизни. Не всем легко изучать язык, поэтому поиск и применение нескольких способов запоминания, которые работают так же хорошо, может оказаться действительно полезным. Важно использовать эффективные способы запоминания и воспроизведения информации, которая имеет первостепенное значение для академического успеха. В этой статье рассматриваются несколько различных методов запоминания при изучении технической лексики английского языка и улучшении памяти у студентов-инженеров.

Ключевые слова: изучение языка, память, способы запоминания, приемы запоминания, мнемотехника.

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THE EFFECTIVE MEMORIZATION METHODS IN LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS

ABSTRACT

English has become the most important language for communication worldwide, but learning it as a foreign language presents multiple challenges. Using a few memorization techniques can make the learning process different when it comes to excelling in career, academics, or everyday life. Not everyone has easy time learning language, so finding and implementing a few memorization techniques that work as well as can be really beneficial. It is important to use the effective ways to remember and recall information which is paramount for academic success. This article covers several different memorization techniques in learning English technical vocabulary and improving memory for engineering students.

Key words: learning language, memory, memorization methods, memorization techniques, and mnemonics.

INTRODUCTION

Memory plays a crucial role in education, which is important in teaching and learning. Every engineering student should have a good memory to comprehend the aspects of language learning such as grammar and vocabulary, skills as listening, reading, writing and speaking, as well as complex formulas and procedures and apply them in problem-solving faced in technical contexts. Usually in engineering classes, it is exposed to vast amounts of information, which is impossible to remember if you don't have good memory retention.

Memory is not just about memorizing information, but also about understanding and applying it. In engineering, it is crucial to understand the underlying principles and concepts behind the formulas and procedures given in technical materials the English language. This requires not only a good memory but also critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Many students complain that they can't remember necessary vocabulary and technical words or phrases in learning engineering material. They understand the content when they read it, but can't recall it later. There is a difference between understanding and remembering. They may understand all the systems of the human body (they make sense when you read about them), but that doesn't mean they'll be able to recall the necessary terms. Fortunately there are memory techniques and strategies to use. Some will be more useful for engineering students in English learning with engineering content.

As it is identified the content the students are working to learn, they will often discover things that they will need to commit to memory. There are numerous strategies that will help them to remember important information effectively so that they can recall it on tests, apply it to subsequent courses, and use it throughout life and career.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The most crucial aspect of language learning is expanding student's vocabulary since it is the foundation for all foreign language proficiency. To communicate fluently in a foreign language, we must gain a thorough understanding of its vocabulary [8]. As a result, it's one of the secrets of reading fluently. It will be simpler for students with large vocabulary sets to comprehend texts that are read aloud. Students that have a large vocabulary will find it easier to practice and use language. According to Saricoban and Balaman [6], vocabulary acquisition is crucial for teaching foreign languages nowadays and cannot be disregarded. Even though vocabulary acquisition was previously accorded

less weight, many seasoned English teachers have come to the conclusion that learning a language entails learning its vocabulary. George Miller [6] asserted that mastery of vocabulary and grammar is a prerequisite for proficiency in speaking, listening, reading, and writing English. The goal of an English class is to help pupils become proficient in vocabulary so that they won't have any challenges as they advance in their education [8].

Moreover, mastering the vocabulary of English involves having a thorough understanding of how to identify, comprehend, and use a wide variety of terms and their meanings. Vocabulary encompasses more than just word meanings, according to Adger [2]. It also involves how a language's vocabulary is organized, including how words are used, stored, and learned, as well as the connections between individual words, phrases, and categories of words and phrases.

In engineering education, memory enables to connect new concepts with previously learned ones, making it easier to comprehend and recall information. It helps to identify patterns and relationships between different topics, making the subject matter more relatable and easier to understand. Additionally, having a good memory helps to be succeed in studying for exams and completing projects within tight deadlines. Moreover, memory plays a vital role in developing your creativity and innovation skills. By having a good memory, you can recall previous solutions to similar problems, modify them, and come up with new and innovative solutions.

Engineering courses are often heavy in content and require a considerable amount of time and effort to comprehend. The technical terminology used in the subject area can make understanding and memorization somewhat difficult. Additionally, poor memory retention may result in poor exam performance, leading to discouragement and loss of confidence in your studies.

However, there are ways to overcome these challenges. One effective method is to use mnemonic devices, which are memory aids that help to remember information. Another method is to practice active recall, which involves recalling information from memory instead of just reading it repeatedly. This method helps strengthen memory and improve retention of information. [3]

Furthermore, taking breaks and getting enough sleep can also help improve memory retention. Studies have shown that sleep plays a crucial role in consolidating memories, meaning that getting enough sleep can help to remember information better.

Finding and implementing a few memorization techniques that work for learning language can be really beneficial for engineering students. There are many different memorization techniques out there that can be used to improve memory.

As an engineering student, it is essential to have an excellent memory retention capacity. Fortunately, there are several techniques that you can use to enhance your memory retention capacity.

The Pomodoro Technique. One of the most effective techniques for enhancing memory retention is the Pomodoro technique. This technique involves breaking down your study time into focused 25-minute sessions, followed by five-minute breaks. The technique helps to maintain concentration and enhance information processing and retention. By taking frequent breaks, it can be avoid burnout and refresh your mind, allowing retaining more information.

Additionally, the Pomodoro technique can help to manage the time effectively. By breaking down study time into smaller chunks, prioritizing the given tasks and allocating the time more efficiently.

Spaced Repetition. Another technique that can help to enhance memory retention capacity is spaced repetition. This technique involves reviewing information periodically until it gets committed to long-term memory. The technique aims to improve retention and prevent the effects of the forgetting curve.

Spaced repetition is particularly effective when studying complex vocabulary topics that require a lot of memorization in language learning. By reviewing the information periodically, reinforce the knowledge and commit it to long-term memory. This technique is also useful when preparing for exams, as it helps to retain information for longer periods.

Mind Mapping. If a student is a visual learner, mind mapping can be an effective technique for enhancing the memory retention capacity. Mind mapping is a visual technique that combines words, images, and color to organize information into a meaningful flow. Through mind mapping, it

is easy to understand complex concepts and information better, including identifying patterns and relationships between different topics and using them.

Mind mapping is also an effective technique for summarizing information. By creating a mind map, it can be condensed large amounts of information into a single page, making it effective to review and retain the information.

The Feynman Technique. The Feynman technique is a learning method that involves taking difficult concepts and breaking them down into simple terms as if you were explaining them to a beginner. The technique enables to understand and retain information better.

By simplifying complex concepts, it helps to improve gaining and understanding of the material deeper and retain the information for longer periods. Additionally, the Feynman technique can help you identify any gaps in your knowledge, allowing you to focus on areas that require more attention.

So, there are several techniques that you can use to enhance the memory retention capacity. By incorporating these techniques into study routine, to improve academic performance and achieve your goals as an engineering student.

Learning words with their context. Students too often learn new vocabulary in isolation. They are provided with a list of words on a particular topic and expected to learn them. This usually involves creating a list of two columns – the word in target language in one and in their mother tongue in the other.

Such drill and repetition exercises do, for some students, work. But for many, the words just don't stick. One way to improve their recall of the words learnt is to encourage students to place the words in an appropriate context. This might be a short example sentence that shows the word being used or it could even be a simple word association. As an additional benefit, this technique also helps students to recall and reiterate the correct use of the word in a sentence.

Tackling difficult words. Students approach learning some words with trepidation – they're long, they look complicated or perhaps they contain lots of diacritics (i.e accents etc.). Often these words are compound words, which are built from two or more smaller words. One effective way to tackle these words and to help memorise them is to try and break them down into their component parts.

In her blog post on the topic, Kirshi Yin has a great example of doing this in Finnish:

“For example, let's take the Finnish word ‘tietokone’, meaning ‘a computer’. At first, I struggled to remember it. It doesn't sound like a computer at all! Suddenly, it came to my mind that ‘kone’ means ‘a machine’. I just had to remember the first part. Later, I saw a similar word — ‘pesukone’, meaning ‘a washing machine’. I already knew the pattern, so it was easier to remember it.” [4].

The Memory Palace. Arguably this is also a form of the mnemonic, but the memory palace is usually categorised as a well-known, stand-alone approach to memory and brain training. Learners commit each item they need to remember (e.g. a list of words, a grammar rule etc) to their long-term memory by associating it with a unique and vivid image. Having done so they also memorise a familiar location (house, school, workspace etc.) with a series of clearly established hot spots. An image (and its associated item) is then associated with or deposited at each hot spot. When prompted for recall, learners retrace a route through the location, stopping at each hot spot, retrieving the image and therefore the to-be-remembered item.

Results and Discussions: Memory improvement relies on understanding how the brain works and the factors that affect the retention of information. The ability to remember and recall information is essential for learning, problem-solving, and decision-making. Memory is a complex process that involves various areas of the brain working together.

The brain's hippocampus is primarily responsible for the formation of new memories. When we learn something new, the hippocampus processes the information and sends it to the appropriate areas of the brain for storage. The prefrontal cortex, located at the front of the brain, is responsible for working memory, which is the ability to hold and manipulate information in the mind for short periods.

How memory works? Memory refers to the process of encoding, storing, and retrieving information. When you learn something new, it must be encoded into the memory through a process called encoding. Encoding involves the conversion of sensory information into a form that can be stored in the brain. The encoded information is then stored in the brain and can be retrieved when required. Repetition and practice enhance the encoding and retrieval process, making it easier to remember the information.

There are two types of memory: short-term memory and long-term memory. Short-term memory is temporary and can hold a limited amount of information for a brief period. Long-term memory, on the other hand, is relatively permanent and can hold vast amounts of information for an extended period which is necessary in language learning.

Factors affecting memory retention. Several factors affect memory retention. These include stress, sleep deprivation, poor nutrition, and lack of exercise. Stress and sleep deprivation hinder the brain's ability to encode and retrieve information, while lack of proper nutrition and exercise can lead to reduced brain functioning.

Chronic stress can damage the hippocampus, leading to memory problems. Sleep deprivation can impair the hippocampus's ability to consolidate memories, making it harder to remember information. Proper nutrition is essential for brain health, and a diet rich in fruits, vegetables, and healthy fats can improve memory and cognitive function. Exercise also plays a vital role in memory improvement by increasing blood flow to the brain and promoting the growth of new brain cells.

Using above mentioned technics and managing time properly, as paying attention to decreasing stress, sleep deprivation, as well as developing the daily plan with exercises in the open air will show effective results not only in learning and using foreign language in studies but it can cause self-development.

CONCLUSION

Vocabulary is the inevitable part of language learning. Today, a great deal of students struggles to learn huge amount of vocabularies in order to pass their exams or have good communication skills with people. While some of them may be successful, most of them fail to use the acquired words in real world speaking environments. So, learning vocabulary does not only mean learning its meaning or form but also requires to gain the ability to use the words when need arises. As much as vocabulary is important, so is the ability to keep the new words in the students' minds. Wenden [9] reminds us of a Chinese proverb that says: "Give a man a fish and he eats for a day, teach him how to fish and he eats for a lifetime". For an effective and meaningful learning, teachers should apply equally effective and meaningful strategies which will not only expose the students to a temporary knowledge of crammed words but a lifetime permanent knowledge base that could be accessed and used forever. [9]

In this study, we have observed that mnemonic technique is highly efficacious than rote learning for pre-intermediate and intermediate level engineering students who are studying English. In addition to that, mnemonic technique does not only help in terms of long term retention, but it also provides motivation for future learning as much as creating a joyful classroom environment. Although it takes a little bit longer than the latter in the sense of time, mnemonic technique compensates that failing by not repeating words in the follow-up period as students can still recall words even after a long time.

Lastly, after having stressed one more time that the mnemonic technique is far superior to the rote learning strategy, this paper intends to point out that in the situations which enable teachers to use mnemonic devices instead of direct memorization, do not waste time with rote learning.

In conclusion, memory plays a vital role in engineering education. It is not just about memorizing information but also about understanding and applying it. Having a good memory can help everyone succeed in studies, develop creativity and innovation skills, and prepare for a successful career in engineering.

Memory retention is critical in the success of engineering students. Incorporating the above-discussed memory improvement techniques alongside developing effective study habits is key to

improving your memory retention capacity. Remember to stay consistent, including incorporating healthy habits such as a nutritious diet and regular exercise!

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